

Face recognition of a missing male after weight loss: Type of photo matters

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Methods of alerting the public about missing individuals, such as AMBER alerts and Silver Alerts, provide photos of the missing individuals. Previous research on alert photos for missing children has shown that recognition declines when the child's current appearance differs from the appearance shown in the alert. For example, school photos typically show a child's face as clean and happy, although the missing child's face may appear dirty and sad. A study manipulated whether the photo of a missing woman in a mock alert showed her with a thin or obese appearance and also manipulated whether her appearance was thin or obese in a recognition photo. When appearance in the alert differed from the recognition photo, recognition was lower. In the current study, we replicated this study but with an adult male as the target. Recognition was significantly lower when the man's appearance at recognition was mismatched in the alert photo. Additionally, there were significant differences in recognition rates by participant gender and ethnicity or race, but not age. The results highlight the importance of providing alert photos for missing persons that are likely to match the appearance of the missing person in terms of weight.

Keywords: alert photos; missing persons; recognition rates; Silver Alerts; weight matching

The ability of people to recognise the faces of missing persons has been the topic of a considerable amount of research for the past three decades (Adjabi et al., 2020). Forensic psychologists and neuroscientists have made significant contributions in this area (e.g., Wang et al., 2019). Research has introduced new techniques for recognising and locating criminals through local (Anwarul & Dahiya, 2020), state-wide, national, and international agencies like the FBI. This research has also influenced the way missing person alerts are communicated to the public. In the past, before the internet and social media became prevalent, missing person alerts were mainly posted in the community or aired on local news channels. Today, alerts for missing individuals are rapidly sent to cell phones and shared across social media, in addition to being broadcast on radio and television. A search for published studies regarding methods of finding missing people on Google Scholar (11/08/2024) yielded 4,880,000 results. These studies ranged from basic face perception research to practical studies focusing on locating criminals, missing children, and elderly individuals. However, little research has been conducted on the ability of people to recognise missing persons who have

Recognition of missing children (amber alerts)

In the United States alone, The FBI National Crime Information Center (NCIC, 2023) reported 375,304 reported entries for missing children in 2023. According to Missing Children Europe data (2023) over 250,000 children go missing in Europe each year, which is about one child every two minutes. In 2022, 66% of reported missing children cases involved children who ran away, 24% involved parental abductions, and 3% involved missing children in migration. Research focussing on face recognition of missing children using mock alerts began appearing in the literature in 2009, and some studies on face aging have also been conducted.

Lampinen et al. (2009) investigated whether shoppers in a supermarket looked at missing children's posters displayed on a bulletin board that customers had to walk past to enter and exit the store. Shoppers were approached by the researchers asking if they would mind taking a short survey as they left the store. Researchers collected demographic data and then asked the shoppers "how long they spent looking at the missing children's photos, whether they intended to search for these children, and how significant they thought the issue of missing children was" (p. 410). Findings indicated that while participants acknowledged the importance of missing children alerts, they did not look at the bulletin board displaying the missing children's posters, citing reasons like being in a rush or distracted by shopping lists. The study revealed that "over 70% of shoppers did not glance at the posters, and more than 20% looked only briefly" (Lampinen et al., 2009, p. 413). These results are troubling for those affected by missing persons.

Even if members of the public attend to missing children alerts, the type of photo shown in an alert may not be effective in helping people to accurately recognise the child. A study in 2009 (Gier & Kreiner) posed an important question: When a child is reported missing and has possibly been abducted, what type of photograph should the caregiver provide to authorities to make it more likely that people will be able to recognise the missing child? The National Center for Missing & Exploited Children (NCMEC, 2023) advises parents to have a clear and recent photo of their child, like a school picture. The researchers noted that if the child missing/abducted had been physically, sexually, or psychologically harmed, their appearance may not resemble their school photo. The researchers used images of four children that showed each child with either a clean and happy appearance (as in a school photograph) or dirty and unkempt, as a missing child may sometimes appear. The researchers manipulated the two types of photos (clean or dirty) both as shown in the missing person alert (these are known as AMBER alerts in the U.S.) and as shown in a recognition phase in which participants were shown photos of the targets and other children and asked to indicate whether they had seen the child in the alert. The results indicated the highest recognition rates when appearance matched at encoding and recognition, e.g., when the alert showed a face with the same appearance type (clean or dirty) as shown in the recognition phase photo. A follow-up study tested four time intervals: intervals of 10 minutes, 3 weeks, 6 weeks, and 12 weeks. Over time, both accuracy and confidence decreased.

Gier et al. (2012) presented a mock AMBER Alert inserted as a commercial while participants watched a television show. Recognition accuracy and confidence were notably lower when the appearance of

the face in the alert differed from the type of appearance shown in recognition photos, similar to the findings of Gier and Kreiner (2009). The researchers suggested that alerts might be more effective with varied photograph types of missing children, especially if one showed the child appearing unkempt. This research contributed to NCMEC revising its advice to parents to provide multiple image types. The researchers suggested research on other vulnerable groups, like elderly individuals, and long-term missing people, to determine the best practices for presenting missing people in alerts.

Recognition of missing senior citizens (silver alerts)

The number of older adults worldwide has greatly risen as the Baby Boomers, who are in their late 60s to 80s now, have aged. After World War II, from 1946 to 1964, the number of births increased dramatically across the globe. European Baby Boomers also represent a significant portion of older individuals, with 20.9% of the population being over 65 years old in 2020, according to Eurostat (2020). Given the fast-growing number of older adults until 2050, it is likely that the count of older adults with dementia or physical limitations will also rise. This could lead to more reported cases of older adults missing due to wandering, often leading to tragic outcomes. The use of alerts for missing older adults, sometimes called Silver Alerts may result in a better chance of the missing person being found. Bindemann et al. (2014) found that famous faces were recognised more often due to the public having more exposure to their faces. The researchers noted their findings apply to identifying faces of older adults from missing person alerts. They suggested if alert posters were more prevalent in the public, recognition of missing seniors may increase.

The first article to investigate recognition based on a mock Silver Alert was published by Gier et al. (2016). The researchers produced four videos featuring an older woman (in her 80s) aimlessly wandering around at a playground where children were playing with family members. In one scenario, the woman wore a nightgown; in another, she wore casual clothes (a long-sleeved blouse and pants). Two control scenarios were also included: one where a different subject replaced the wandering woman, and another without any older adult present. The researchers hypothesised that recognition would be better in the nightgown condition due to the uniqueness of wearing a nightgown in a public park; however, recognition was higher for woman in casual dress. The study did not show any differences based on age, race, or gender of the participants. One concerning aspect of the findings was that only 3% of the 330 participants recognised the older woman in her nightgown, who was clearly showing dementia signs, such as Alzheimer's disease.

Gier and Kreiner (2020) tested whether watching an educational video on the importance of Silver Alerts before viewing a Silver Alert would lead to better target recognition. Results indicated that those who watched the video had higher chances of correctly identifying the missing woman than those who did not. Moreover, women participants identified the missing woman more accurately than did men, and Caucasian participants recognised the missing person (who was Caucasian) better than African American participants. Finally, individuals with more experience with older adults were more likely to recognise the missing woman. These findings imply that a brief informational segment before showing a missing person alert on television could enhance its effectiveness.

While several studies on Silver Alerts (e.g., Gier & Kreiner, 2020; Gier et al., 2017) studied recognition of a missing, elderly Caucasian person, little research has examined recognition for individuals of other races or ethnicities. Black older adults are at the highest risk of developing AD (Steenland et al., 2016). Gier and Kreiner (2017) presented short videos of a Black couple while wearing glasses or not wearing glasses, as well as versions in which the man and woman appeared separately. The results indicated partial support for the matching hypothesis that recognition would be greatest when the target's appearance in the missing person alert matched the recognition photo (e.g., wearing glasses at both encoding and recognition). Matching appearance, in terms of wearing glasses, may only affect recognition in some situations, possibly dependent on unique factors associated with each face. For example, the man was recognised more often with glasses, and the woman was recognised more without glasses. It is also interesting to note that the results were not consistent with the idea that participants could rely entirely on the presence of the glasses as a visual cue to identify the target. The

results suggest that we should not assume that individuals are equal or even similar in the likelihood that they will be recognised by the public, as the ability to recognise them may depend on specific facial characteristics as well as how they appear in an alert.

Recognition of long-term missing persons

Studies on long-term missing persons are sparse in the literature. There are articles on the effects on families of a long-term missing child (DeYoung & Buzzi, 2003), as well as face-age progression studies (e.g. Lampinen et al., 2009), but little research has been done to test the effectiveness of an alert for a child who has been missing for a number of years. An exception is Gier and Kreiner's (2022) study using a video of a missing child shown at age 7 with recognition photos of the child at ages 7, 10, 13, 16, 18, 19, and 20. Each alert showed a photo of the target at age 7, and then a photo of her at a different age. The results showed that when her hair length was the same as the child's in the video (long) and the recognition photo showed her at the same age (7), recognition was high. Parents of real long-term missing children often have face-aged photos made of their children, and according to NCMEC some of these attempts have been successful. The take-home message from this study is to keep current photos of children and offer these photos to law enforcement in case a child is missing. For example, often when a child is abducted his/her hair is changed, such as colouring the hair, and/or cutting the hair. Other changes can be made to make the child appear to be of a different gender.

Gier et al. (2023) tested the recognition of a woman missing for 10 years. The photo of the target female was at age 29, and the missing person alert showed her at 39 years of age. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of significant weight loss/gain on face recognition. The missing woman in the study had weight loss surgery and her before/after photos were significantly different in appearance. Participants (a total of 732) viewed one of two missing person alerts of the target. One alert showed her at age 29, and the other at age 39. For participants in the age 29 condition. For the 29-year-old condition, the location of where she had last been seen was stated in the alert to make the alert seem more realistic. For the 39-year-old condition, a current photo of her was used in the alert. In this condition, participants were told in the alert that the missing lady had been in a car accident and had amnesia and no information was available. The results showed, similar to results of Gier and Kreiner's studies on Amber Alerts (2009; 2012), that when participants saw her at 29, and then in the recognition phase saw her again at age 29 (in a different photo), recognition was high. When participants were in conditions where her appearance changed markedly (in weight and age), recognition rates were low. For individuals who undergo weight loss surgery or otherwise experience a large change in weight, the transformation of the face and body can significantly affect the recognition of the person. In the current study, we replicate Gier et al. (2023) but with a missing person who is a man instead of a woman.

Individual differences in relation to face recognition

Age differences

Past studies have shown when participants are presented with multiple photographs of different aged people, recognition of people of a similar age as the participants tends to be greater (Hills, 2012; Wright & Stroud, 2002). This difference based on age has been shown for older adults (Strickland-Hughes et al., 2020), young adults (Rhodes & Anastasi, 2012), and children (Hills & Lewis, 2011). Age differences in recognition also appear to be partially dependent on experience with different age groups (Harrison & Hole, 2009). Faces that were once own-age become other-age, which indicates that a recent experience appears to moderate the differences more so than historical experience (Hills, 2012).

Gender differences

Multiple studies have shown that females outperform males on face recognition (Lewin & Herlitz, 2002; McClure, 2000), with larger differences than those found based on participant age or race/ethnicity (Herlitz et al., 1997; Herlitz & Yonker, 2002; Lewin et al., 2001; Wahlin et al., 1993).

Some researchers have suggested that women outperform males based on their verbal label ability (Herlitz et al., 1997; Herlitz & Yonker, 2002; Lewin et al., 2001), whereas other studies have reported female proficiency specifically at recognizing other female faces (McKelvie, 1981). Some studies have shown that females can even outperform males in face recognition of female faces, as well as recognizing male faces if no female photos are present (Herlitz & Lovén, 2013).

Race and ethnicity differences

An early study on face recognition for people with races/ethnicities differing from the participant was reported by Feingold (1914), who found that own race/ethnicity faces were recognised with more accuracy than faces of other ethnicities. Later studies have continued to find support for an own-race effect (Cross et al., 1971; Gross, 2009; Mukudi & Hills, 2019; Shapiro & Penrod, 1986). Researchers have suggested that once an individual categorises a face as a member of an out-group versus an in-group, motivation for deep processing is reduced, leading to weaker and less effective processing of individuating features (Bernstein et al., 2007; Fiske & Neuberg, 1990; Rodin, 1987).

Bernstein et al. (2007) proposed a social categorization-individuation model (SCI) that has three factors that contribute to the own-group differences and include “social categorisation, perceiver motivation, and perceiver experience with other-group faces” (Mukudi & Hills, 2019, p. 2). Based on this model, a higher the level of motivation to process individual faces will produce more individualization. If quality time is spent with people from other ethnic groups, face recognition will change from categorization (e.g. Caucasian, African American, Hispanic) to individuation (focusing on specific facial details such as eye shape and colour, nose and mouth shape, or any distinguishing features). Mukudi and Hills (2019) found that face recognition accuracy decreased when the number of out-group facial features increased. These findings are particularly relevant for studies with samples of college students that are not overwhelmingly one race/ethnicity.

What if an adult male had been missing for 10 years and during that time had undergone a major weight change? If the missing person's alert photo did not reflect that change in appearance, would it reduce the ability of people to recognise the person? Based on previous studies of missing person alerts with children (Gier & Kreiner, 2009, Gier & Kreiner, 2012) showing higher recognition accuracy when the appearance of the child in an alert was similar to the appearance of the child in recognition photos, we hypothesised that recognition rates would be higher for a missing adult male when weight-related appearance matched between encoding (i.e., as shown in an alert) and recognition (i.e., when a member of the public might later encounter the missing person; in our study, the recognition phase involves showing participants a set of photos including both the missing person and other people who did not appear in the alert). Additionally, Gier et al. (2023) study of a long-term missing woman showed the same pattern. In addition, we hypothesised that participants' confidence in their recognition of the missing man would be greater when appearance at encoding matched appearance at recognition. Based on previous research, we predicted differences in recognition rates depending on participant gender and race/ethnicity, but not a difference based on age, due to limited variability in age in our university student sample.

METHODS

Participants

A total of 232 individuals accessed the online study. We deleted data from 18 individuals who completed less than 90% of the study, resulting in a sample size of 214. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 67 years with a mean age of 23.96 years (SD = 6.55). Participants reported their race/ethnicity as follows: White 153 (71.5%), Black or African American 38 (17.8%), Hispanic 10 (4.7%), Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander 5 (2.3%), Asian 4 (1.9%), Other 4 (1.9%). The sample included 124 (57.9%) individuals identifying as male and 90 (42.1%) identifying as female. We recruited participants at a southern U.S. university using Sona, an online research participation management system.

Materials and procedure

We presented stimuli and collected responses using Qualtrics, an online research platform. Participants completed a demographic survey including age, gender, and race/ethnicity.

We randomly assigned participants to one of four missing person conditions for the same 30-year-old male. One independent variable consisted of whether the missing person alert showed the man before (morbidly obese) or after (thin) weight-loss surgery. The other independent variable was whether the man's photo shown in the recognition phase showed him with the before-surgery or after-surgery appearance (See Figure 3).

In between presenting the missing person alert and the recognition phase, a memory task was used as a distractor. The memory task included presenting 114 compound words. In the recognition phase of the study, participants saw 10 foil photographs, each displaying a man who appeared similar to the target shown in the alert, in addition to the target photo of the actual missing person. The photos appeared in random order for five seconds each. After each photo, the participants were asked: Was this male in the missing person alert? Their choices were "yes" or "no". They were then asked to rate their confidence in their decision using a visual antilog scale of 0-100. Following the recognition phase of the study, participants read a debriefing statement about the purpose of the study.

RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the percentage of participants who correctly recognised the target in each of the four conditions corresponding to appearance in the alert (before or after the weight loss procedure) and appearance at recognition. A chi-square test of independence indicated a significant relationship between response to the target photo and condition, $\chi^2(N=214) = 37.30, p < .001$. We compared the recognition rates for each condition using the z-test for proportions; the before/before condition had significantly higher recognition than the before/after and after/before conditions, and the after/after condition had significantly higher recognition than the before/after condition.

Figure 1
Percent target recognition by condition-before and after weight loss

Figure 2
Mean target confidence rating by condition

Figure 3

Missing person alerts and examples of foils in the recognition phase of the study

Alert: Missing Male Before Weight Loss

Alert: Missing Male After Weight Loss

Recognition Phase: Target Thin

Recognition Phase: Target Obese

Example of Foils Seen in the Recognition Phase of the Study

Example of Foils in the Obese Condition

Example of Foils in the Thin Condition

Figure 4

Comparison studies to current study on target hits by condition (matched versus mismatched photos)
Current study percent recognition – Gier & Kreiner (2024)

The effect of weight loss/gain on the recognition of a long-term missing person (Gier et al., 2023)

Figure 5
Comparison pattern of results for AMBER alerts

Memory of children's faces by adults: appearance does matter. Gier & Kreiner (2009).

AMBER alerts: Are school-type photographs the best choice for identifying missing children?
Gier et al. (2012).

We conducted a simultaneous logistic regression predicting target recognition (no = 0, yes = 1) from alert type, recognition type, and the interaction of alert and recognition. We also included the demographic variables of age in years, gender (coded as 0 = male, 1 = female), and race/ethnicity. The race/ethnicity variable was recoded into three groups due to the number of participants: Caucasian (n = 153); African American (n = 38), and Hispanic/Native American or Pacific Islander/Asian/Other (n = 23), entered into the regression model as two dummy variables. The regression model was significant, $\chi^2(7, N = 214) = 65.15, p < .001$, Nagelkerke $R^2 = .339$. As shown in Table 1, alert type, recognition type, and the alert by recognition interaction were significant predictors of target recognition. Gender was also a significant predictor, with females (65.6%) recognizing the target at a higher rate than males (51.6%). Each of the race/ethnicity variables was a significant predictor, with Caucasians (64.7%) having a higher recognition rate than African Americans (39.5%) or individuals in the Hispanic/Native American or Pacific Islander/Asian/Other group (39.1%). Of the significant predictors, the alert type by recognition type interaction was the most important in predicting target recognition, with an Exp(B) value of 33–44.

Individuals who recognised the target provided slightly higher predictions of recognition ($M = 76.03, SD = 19.35$) compared to those who did not recognise the target ($M = 71.96, SD = 20.85$), but the difference was not significant, $t(211) = 1.80, p = .074, d = .249$. There was not a significant difference in confidence ratings for predictions of recognition between those who did ($M = 79.49, SD = 19.38$) and did not ($M = 76.14, SD = 20.61$) recognise the target, $t(212) = 1.22, p = .226, d = .168$.

We conducted two-way between subjects' ANOVAs with alert type and recognition type as independent variables. The dependent variables were target confidence rating, foil confidence rating, and false alarm rates. For target confidence, there were not significant effects of alert type, $F(1, 210) = 0.52, p = .473, \eta^2 = .00$ or recognition type, $F(1, 210) = 2.00, p = .159, \eta^2 = .01$, but there was a significant interaction, $F(1, 210) = 13.73, p < .001, \eta^2 = .06$. As shown in Figure 2, target confidence was higher for in the conditions in which appearance matched than in conditions in which there was a mismatch in appearance.

For foil confidence, there were not significant main effects of alert type, $F(1, 210) = 0.90, p = .347, \eta^2 = .00$, recognition type, $F(1, 210) = 0.02, p = .878, \eta^2 = .00$, or the interaction, $F(1, 210) = 1.93, p = .166, \eta^2 = .01$.

For false alarm rates, there were no significant main effects of alert type, $F(1, 210) = 1.40, p = .238, \eta^2 = .01$, recognition type, $F(1, 210) = 0.42, p = .516, \eta^2 = .00$, or the interaction, $F(1, 210) = 3.84, p = .051, \eta^2 = .02$. False alarm rates were as follows: before/before (6.4%), before/after (8.6%), after/before (7.7%), after/after (3.4%), reflecting a non-significant trend for higher false alarm rates in the conditions in which appearance did not match.

DISCUSSION

We investigated how well adults could recognise the face of a man when he differed in appearance, based on a major weight change, from appearance as shown in a missing person alert. As we hypothesised, participants were more likely to recognise the man when his appearance in the recognition photo matched his appearance in the alert (e.g., obese/obese or thin/thin) compared to when there was a mismatch in obese or thin appearance. The variability in recognition rates was large, with participants recognizing the missing man 81% of the time in the before/before condition (with an obese appearance at both encoding and recognition), compared to 27% recognition in the mismatched before/after condition. Note that the latter condition is a likely situation for a missing person who undergoes major weight loss (perhaps as a result of weight-loss surgery) between the time he goes missing and the time a missing person alert is posted. It is also worth noting that participants tended to be more confident in their recognition responses when the man had an obese appearance at both encoding and recognition. It is possible that the obese appearance was more noticeable and memorable compared to the thin appearance.

We hypothesised that female participants would recognise the missing person at a higher rate than male participants, and the results supported this hypothesis. This finding is consistent with previous research showing that females typically outperform males in face recognition. Rehnman and Herlitz (2007) tested both women and girls and men and boys on face recognition of same and opposite-sex photos. Regardless of age or ethnicity, females (both women and girls) outperformed men and boys. Other studies (Ino et al., 2010; Lewin & Herlitz, 2002) found similar results.

Our results showed that participant race/ethnicity and age were not significant predictors of recognition. Previous research has shown own-race effects in which individuals showed better recognition of faces matching their own race/ethnicity (Gross, 2009; Mukudi & Hills, 2019; Shapiro & Penrod, 1986). As the missing man in the current study was Caucasian, we might have therefore expected the Caucasian participants would show an advantage in recognizing him, but this was not the case. A possible explanation is that, unlike studies done to test for own-race/ethnicity differences that used multiple faces for recognition, the present study used only one target photo as our goal was to investigate face recognition in the case of a missing man who might have undergone a major weight change. The ability to recognise faces of individuals of different races and ethnicities is likely to differ depending on the features of the individuals' faces. As expected, based on the limited age variability in a university student sample, we also found that participant age was a significant predictor of recognition.

LIMITATIONS

Our study had several limitations that need to be mentioned. First, our sample was limited in several demographic characteristics, as we used convenience sampling to obtain a sample of university students. It would be helpful for further research to purposefully recruit people of different ages of interest from the university or community to determine how well the results generalise beyond a university student population.

We collected data for the present study using an online research platform. The disadvantages include being unable to proctor the experiment to ensure that participants follow instructions and pay sufficient attention. We made the alert slides slow enough to read and comprehend, but fast enough to discourage using a cell phone to take a photo of the alert. Additionally, the photos in the recognition phase appeared for five seconds each, then the next page showed the questions over the photo of the male presented. Based on the results of our study, we think it is unlikely that participants used methods like taking photos of the alert, as we observed low recognition rates in the mismatched conditions.

Future research should explore more effective ways of increasing face recognition of a long-term missing person. Studies of missing person alerts, as displayed on cell phones, would help us better understand how effective those alerts might be compared to alerts shown on television screens or posted on hard-copy flyers.

With the popularity of face-age progression for finding long-term missing people, research should explore factors influencing what a person could look like other than the traditional comparison of family members and bone structure. When losing significant weight, for instance, the face will appear differently to those who knew the missing person and to strangers. Another important factor to explore is gender identity. For example, if a teen or young adult is questioning his/her gender, it is possible the person could later be transgender. The associated changes in appearance could make it harder to recognise the person. Family members may not think to ask for an age-progressed face of their missing adult child both male and female. According to Herman et al. (2022), transgender and gender-diverse (TGD) are among the fastest-growing populations. As of June 2022, an "estimated 1.6 million individuals in the U.S. alone identify as transgender or gender diverse, or approximately 0.5% of the adult population and 1.4% of youth aged 13–17" (Herman et al., 2022, para. 2).

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study were similar to Gier and Kreiner's findings (2009; 2012) showing that recognition of children was increased when their appearance in recognition photos matched with their appearance as shown in an alert accuracy was high. Additionally, a current study by Gier et al. (2023) showed similar results as did the current study. In Figure 4 we show the comparison between target recognition from the current study and Gier et al. (2023) study. In Figure 5 we show two AMBER studies showing the same pattern. Our current study extends that pattern of results to an adult man, with appearance differing (or matching) based on a major weight change, as compared to the appearance of the children varying in whether they appeared clean or dirty.

Based on the present results, it may be advisable when a person goes missing to consider using age-face progression with one photo of the missing person at a significantly different weight than when they went missing. Recognition of the person would be less likely if the missing person had gained/lost a significant amount of weight. A substantial weight gain or loss may influence recognising the person, and members of the public may dismiss any person or photo that does not immediately appear to be similar. Similar points about other possible changes in appearance, such as those related to a change in gender identity (e.g., hair length, breast size, changes in attire).

The present research provides additional support for the importance of the similarity between a missing person as shown in an alert and how they may currently appear. One approach to mitigate how changes in appearance may reduce recognition is to provide a range of photos and/or videos showing the person with differing appearance (either naturally or using software to generate images) and then to use a variety of the photos in missing person alerts. Finding consistent patterns in face recognition is an important contribution to the literature on missing people. We hope that continued research in this area will result in a greater likelihood of missing people being found.

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